

Evaluation of Interaction Parameter and Hence Stoichiometry in the Complexes of all-cis-1,2,3,4-Cyclopentanetetracarboxylic Acid with Some Di and Trivalent Metals

G. A. RAMA RAO and K. SRINIVASULU

School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain-466 010

Manuscript received 31 March 1979, accepted 5 November 1980

Formation constants of the complexes of all-cis-1,2,3,4-cyclopentanetetracarboxylic acid (CPTA) with Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Ga(III), Y(III) and Al(III) have been determined potentiometrically at various ionic strengths in ClO₄⁻ back ground in aqueous medium at 25°. The stoichiometry of the complex species in each system has been confirmed by applying presumed values of interionic interaction parameter with the use of stability constants data. The value of the parameter is a factor of stoichiometry. The equation of Scatchard involving a factor relating the size of ions has been employed to calculate the stability constants at zero ionic strength for various values of interaction parameter. The best fit value of the parameter has been found out by the use of standard deviation method instead of curve fitting method. The value of the parameter which is ~3.5 suggests that all the systems have a 1 : 1 stoichiometry which is in agreement with the results of ratio titrations by pH metric method.

CYCLOPENTANETETRACARBOXYLIC acid (CPTA) was used as a selective reagent for the gravimetric determination of zirconium¹. Its different compounds were used for various purposes such as resins and rubber preparation² and its tetraesters for plasticizers³. Hitherto its complexation behaviour has not been studied although as a quadridentate ligand it has been of great interest in coordination chemistry. The present work deals with a systematic study of complexation of CPTA with Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Ga(III), Y(III) and Al(III) at six ionic strengths to evaluate the mean distance of approach by a statistical method instead of curve fitting method suggested by earlier workers^{4,5}. The assumed value for ionic interaction parameter (mean distance) helps in confirming the stoichiometry of the complex system as obtained from ratio titrations in aqueous solutions⁶.

Experimental

All solutions were prepared from AnalaR grade chemicals and standardized by conventional methods. Freshly prepared sodium hydroxide solution free from carbonate was used.

Cyclopentanetetracarboxylic acid of Matheson Coleman & Bell Co., U.S.A., m.p. 195-196°; mol. wt. 246.17 was used.

pH measurements were carried out with a pH meter (pH 821, Electronic Corporation of India make) with an expanded scale having an accuracy of ± 0.02 units pH and sensitivity ± 0.01 at 25°.

The titration procedure was followed as recommended by Irving and Rossotti⁷ by the

addition of appropriate amount of 1M sodium perchlorate solution to maintain the desired ionic strength.

Results and Discussion

The metal-ligand formation constants were calculated by the method⁷ involving the calculation of free ligand concentration and are given in Table 1. The increase of ionic strength is found to

TABLE 1—STOICHIOMETRIC STABILITY CONSTANTS OF DI AND TRIVALENT METALS AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS

Ionic strength μ	Hg(II)	Cd(II)	Zn(II)	Ga(III)	Y(III)	Al(III)
0.05	10.65	9.90	8.14	11.73	11.63	11.03
0.10	9.48	9.40	7.75	10.77	10.72	10.13
0.15	9.15	8.97	7.28	10.20	10.03	9.35
0.17	9.02	8.77	7.00	9.92	9.65	9.26
0.19	8.71	8.58	—	9.60	9.20	8.75
0.23	7.92	7.75	6.29	9.30	8.47	8.22

decrease the stability value which is not unusual in many complex systems. The analysis of stability constants data by Bronsted⁸ equation did not yield any useful information as expected since it lacks the factor relating the size of ions.

The equation of Scatchard⁹

$$\log K = \log K^{\circ} + \frac{2A Z_A Z_B \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \beta a_1 \sqrt{\mu}} \quad \dots (1)$$

involving a factor considering the size of the ions has been applied, where $\log K$ is the stability constant at particular ionic strength, $\log K^\circ$ is the stability constant at zero ionic strength, A and β are the Debye-Hückel constants having the values 0.509 and 0.3286×10^8 respectively and ' a_1 ' is an interionic interaction parameter. The computation of ' a_1 ' was done by earlier workers by a graphical method putting different trial values of a_1 in the above equation and observing its influence on the $\log K^\circ$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ plots. In the present investigation the evaluation of ' a_1 ' value has been made more precise by calculating the average standard deviation employing the relation

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{(B_1 - \bar{B})^2}{r}} \quad \dots (2)$$

where B_1 = any individual value (ie) $\log K^\circ$; \bar{B} = the arithmetical mean of the values of $\log K^\circ$ and r = the number of experimental values involved in the calculation of \bar{B} .

It is expected that for a correct value of a_1 the average δ value is minimum and the a_1 values are 3.4, 3.4 and 3.6 for Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) respectively and 3.4 in case of trivalent metals.

The variation of $\log K^\circ$ vs $\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \beta a_1 \sqrt{\mu}}$ was found to

be exhibiting the linear behaviour in a better way than in the case of $\log K$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ in all cases.

The a_1 values obtained in this work suggest that the complexes are of 1 : 1 type^{4,5}.

These complexes behave as ion-pairs in aqueous solutions. The complexes have been isolated in aqueous medium as insoluble species and their solubility in non-polar solvents is insignificant. The infrared spectra of these solid complexes indicate a primarily ionic linkage between metal and

ligand. In view of the large values obtained for the slopes in all the cases it is not unreasonable to suppose that it is at the present time not possible to propose a mechanism for the interacting ions in the complex. Hence the method has been applied only to calculate the thermodynamic stability constants at zero ionic strength and to confirm the stoichiometry with the help of the values of average distance of closest approach, as observed from the ratio titrations. The thermodynamic stability constants at zero ionic strength have been calculated as 11.63, 11.18, 9.45 for the metals Hg(II), Cd(II) and Zn(II) respectively and 13.95, 13.90 and 13.52 in case of Ga(III), Y(III) and Al(III) respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the CSIR for the award of research fellowship to one of them (G.A.R.) and to Prof. M. M. Bokadia for his interest in the progress of the work.

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